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“STRANGE FEELING”

Leap those odd days that bustle
Together we build a new castle
Minding each other with no hassle
Only wind passes our ears that whistle.

Better to have a strange feeling
Like stars that keep on shining
Memories shared cause me smiling
To just forget pain, I am dwelling.

Thinking of you is not an option
Always on the top of my decision
Leaving without any regression
To have you on my final destination.

